

School mathematics as a tool for spreading religious fundamentalism: The case of ‘Vedic mathematics’ in India

Jayasree Subramanian, SRM University, jayasree.subramanian@gmail.com

There is a widely held belief that mathematics and school mathematics curriculum are apolitical even though critical thinkers in mathematics education have challenged this claim and pointed to how the larger socio-political context determines what mathematics is, what mathematics should be taught in school and how it should be taught. Often the political nature of mathematics is hidden from us. This paper seeks to argue that while holding on to the belief that mathematics is apolitical, there is an attempt by a certain section in India to use school mathematics curriculum as a tool to spread Hindu religious fundamentalism and that Vedic mathematics becomes an ideal component for achieving this. The paper also seeks to argue that Vedic mathematics would alienate not just the religious minorities but also those from the marginalized castes.

Introduction

This paper addressed to the MES community in the first place and to all committed to the cause of building a more egalitarian world, arises out of a serious anxiety that in an increasingly globalized academic world, in our interest to be inclusive, we might unwittingly promote voices from geopolitical margins, unaware of the fact that some of these are voices of the locally oppressive forces. This is truly a complex issue given that power and hierarchy operate form multiple social structures or institutions which may or may not intersect and hence it is not possible to classify a person clearly as either an oppressor or an oppressed-one could be both. Moreover, operating in the globalized academic world, what is visible to us immediately are the global hierarchies such as the north-south divide, racism, white supremacy, eurocentrism, and so on. So, for example seen from outside, India would be visible as a developing, low-income country, perhaps also as an ancient civilization with a rich history, including significant achievements in mathematics, available in the ancient Indian language Sanskrit. Caste as a significant structure in India, its relationship to language, the rise of Hindu religious fundamentalism and the systematic effort on the part of the Hindu fundamentalist to distort history, including the history of mathematics in India are perhaps less likely to be visible. One reason why hierarchies present in the geopolitical margins, are invisible in the globalized academia is because, typically those who represent

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the geopolitical margins are the beneficiaries of and hence blind to the existence of the local hierarchies. There is therefore an urgent need to seek out alternate perspectives that challenge the dominant voices from marginalized geopolitical locations. And there is also a responsibility on the part of the scholars from geopolitical margins to foreground the voices of those who are marginalized in their location. I would like to discuss the case of Vedic mathematics both as a possible example of the above situation and as an instance of how school mathematics becomes a tool for spreading religious fanaticism in India.

Mathematics is generally believed to be apolitical, partly because of the prevalent notion that there is only one mathematics which has applications in several contexts. Even though this belief has been challenged by critical thinkers (who argue that mathematics, like any other body of knowledge is socially constructed and is shaped by the beliefs and values of a community of practitioners who bring a form of mathematics into existence), outside the small community engaged in mathematics education research, the dominant notions about mathematics as apolitical and universal continue to prevail. Mathematics education, with its dubious reputation of acting as a gate keeper to the socio-economically marginalized learners, is well recognised as deeply political, serving the interest of the socially and structurally privileged. However, in the Indian context with very little research in mathematics education, both mathematics and mathematics education continue to be seen as apolitical. Against this backdrop, there is an attempt by Hindu right-wing elements to use mathematics as a political tool to promote religious fundamentalism in India by incorporating 'Vedic mathematics' in school curriculum. The term 'Vedic mathematics' invokes images of mathematics and mathematicians of ancient India, of a form of mathematics that has something to do with the Vedas and written in Sanskrit. Seen from outside India 'Vedic mathematics' could well be an instance of ethnomathematics and seen from within the country, it could instil pride in India in the minds of the learner. I would discuss what is 'Vedic mathematics' and what is the politics behind incorporating 'Vedic mathematics' in school curriculum. Using mathematics as a political tool has parallels in other contexts. Vithal and Skovsmose (1997) discuss in detail how, in the name of cultural diversity and ethnomathematics, an inferior form of mathematics was taught to students coming from the bottom of the hierarchy, during the apartheid regime in South Africa.

A myth called 'Vedic mathematics'

In the year 1965 a book titled *Vedic Mathematics* was posthumously published under the name of a monk Bharati Krishna Tirthaji, who was a Shankaracharya (religious head) of Govardhana Peetham in Puri, Odisha. The book was brought out by Motilal Banarsidass publishers. Bharati Krishna Tirthaji (whose name at the time of his birth and till he became a monk was Venkataraman) studied mathematics and secured a MA in mathematics from American College of Sciences in Rochester, New York, writing the examinations from Mumbai before he took the religious path. The book, available in English, consists of 16 sutras or simple mathematical formulae. While the Shankaracharya claimed that these formulae are part of a parishishta (supplementary text / appendix) to Atharvaveda, this claim

could not be established. Dani, a professor of mathematics who has been writing consistently to dispel the myth of Vedic mathematics says that K.S.Shukla, a renowned scholar of ancient Indian mathematics, on one occasion personally met the Shankaracharya and requested him to point out the sutras in the parishishta of the Atharvaveda, only to be told by the Shankaracharya that the 16 sutras demonstrated by him 'occurred in his own parishishta and not any other' and even this supplementary text alluded to by Shankaracharya does not seem to exist in Sanskrit (Dani, 1993). Clearly, the fact that the sutras are not found in any appendix to Atharvaveda must have attracted a lot of attention even at the time of publication of the book because the general editor to the book V. S. Agrawala and Manjula Trivedi, who has written the note 'My beloved Gurudeva' on the Shankaracharya, feel compelled to address this issue. Agrawala tries to explain this away by saying the word Veda, according to the Shankaracharya himself, refers to 'the fountainhead and illimitable storehouse of all knowledge' and since 'the Vedas as traditionally accepted in India as the repository of all knowledge should be and not what they are in human possession' (Tirthaji, 1965, p. 6). Manjula Trivedi says 'Obviously these formulae are not to be found in the present recensions of Atharvaveda; they were actually reconstructed, on the basis of intuitive revelation, from materials scattered here and there in the Atharvaveda' (Tirthaji, 1965, p. x).

The issue is not about the validity of the 16 formulae. They are valid and provide quicker methods to solve some problems and are at the level that they could be incorporated in school mathematics. The formulae have been compared to similar work by Trachtenberg and others. Dani says

the material in the swamiji's book looks like a compilation of tricks in elementary arithmetic and algebra, discovered by some intelligent hobbyists. What it contains are ways of working out some classes of computations; in certain special cases these ways turn out to be faster than the standard school-book methods (Dani, 1993, pp. 1579–1580).

The issue at hand about *Vedic Mathematics* is not the mathematical content, but the adjective 'Vedic' attached to it. The natural question that arises is, why did the Shankaracharya claim that the sutras are found in an appendix to Atharvaveda when they are not and why was the book titled *Vedic Mathematics* instead of something like *A Bunch of Formulae* or *Some Interesting Mathematical Shortcuts*? Does this have anything to do with the rise of Hindu Nationalism in India, the status of Veda in Hindu religion, the status of Shankaracharya, the position of Hinduism vis-à-vis other religions in India?

Vedic Mathematics and the agenda of Hindu Supremacy

The book *Vedic Mathematics* appears in post-independent India, in the year 1965, five years after the author's death. With the enduring contributions of the mathematical genius Srinivasa Ramanujan, with the contributions of several other notable mathematicians of the 19th and 20th century, with the work of P. C. Mahalanobis and C. R. Rao in statistics, with the establishment of premier research institutes in post independent India, there was a lot of hope for India to make lasting contributions to modern mathematics and statistics when the book *Vedic Mathematics* was in the making. Research on Ancient Indian mathematics also

led to important publications such as the volumes *History of Hindu Mathematics* by Dutta and Narain (1962), *Ancient Indian Mathematics and Vedha* by Gurjar (1947), the papers by T. A. Saraswathi Amma (1959, 1961) on geometry in ancient and medieval India and more, apart from the works of W. E. Clark (1930), G. R. Kaye (1915). At least 11 doctoral theses were written on the history of mathematics before 1960 (Gupta, 1993). Therefore, in post-independent India, still young at the time the Shankaracharya was working towards the book, there was much to look forward to both by way of researching the past achievements in mathematics and making a mark in modern mathematics. Then why did the Shankaracharya write a book of 16 formulae and call it *Vedic Mathematics*?

One could try and find an answer to this question from the preface to the book by the Shankaracharya, where it becomes clear that the Shankaracharya's concern is more with establishing the supremacy of Vedas. Towards this end, he begins by first reinterpreting the term 'Vedas' to mean a repository of all knowledge across all disciplines that existed in the past, that exists now and that could ever exist. This interpretation would establish the supremacy of Vedas and the work left for the committed servants of the religion is to demonstrate this to the world. It is important to note that the period when the Shankaracharya invests himself with this work is also the period when Hindu Nationalism is on the rise in India. In the early 20th century, Hindutva emerges as a strong force seeking to establish the superiority of Hinduism over western superiority and challenging the spread of Islam and Christianity in India. Shankaracharya's work in mathematics is in response to the poor representation of ancient Indian mathematical knowledge by western scholars. In the words of the Shankaracharya:

And the contemptuous or, at best patronising attitude adopted by some so-called Orientalists, Indologists, antiquarians, research scholars etc., who condemned, or light-heartedly nay, irresponsibly, frivolously and flippantly dismissed, several abstruse-looking and recondite parts of the Vedas as "sheer-nonsense"-or as "infant-humanity's prattle", and so on, merely added fuel to the fire (so to speak) and further confirmed and strengthened our resolute determination to unravel the too-long hidden mysteries of philosophy and science contained in ancient India's Vedic lore, with the consequence that, after eight years of concentrated contemplation in forest solitude, we were at long last able to recover the long lost keys which alone could unlock the portals thereof. (Tirthaji, 1965, pp. xiv-xv)

So, his aim was to 'demonstrate' that all the western mathematical knowledge is already found in the Vedas. He does this by saying that he developed strong intuitions in mathematics after eight years of concentrated contemplation and discovered the 16 formulae in a parishishta or appendix of the Atharvaveda. These 16 sutras according to him, can solve the toughest mathematical problems that the present day advanced western mathematics is trying hard to solve spending a lot of time and energy. He also lists 11 topics in the western mathematics and says all these are covered by the 16 sutras and declares 'there is no part of mathematics pure or applied, which is beyond their jurisdiction' and adds that if one spends 2 to 3 hours per day for one year all the mathematics that one learns in western universities spending 16 to 20 years.

To sum up, this is a clear case in which a religious head who commands a lot of respect among the Hindus comes up with 16 formulae which can make some computations simpler and wilfully makes false claims namely, they are part of the Vedas and they are as good as all the mathematics taught in the western universities today, and the Vedic methods are so superior that they can be learnt in one twentieth of the time it takes to learn western mathematics.

These claims have met with serious criticism from some of the well-established mathematicians and scientists from India and abroad (Dani, 1993, 2001, 2007, 2012; Raju, 2014a, 2014b; Narlikar, 2003; Bal, 2010; Singh, 2020; Plofker, 2009; Shukla, 1991). Some of the leading mathematicians from the country signed and sent a letter to the National Council of Education Research and Training saying what passes off as Vedic mathematics is 'Neither Vedic Nor Mathematics'. But these criticisms have had very little impact on the spread of Vedic mathematics in India.

Vedic Mathematics: A meeting point for religious and economic right wing

Vedic mathematics started getting introduced in school once Bhartiya Janata Party (BJP), a Hindu right wing political party came to power in four states in India in the year 1991 (Jayaraman, 1997). In the last two decades there have been a flurry of activities around Vedic mathematics. Just a search in google scholar will lead one to hundreds of research publications by Indian scholars which are based on Vedic mathematics, in computer science. In contrast Vedic mathematics has not received any attention from the international academic community if we leave out a handful of books and articles by authors from outside India.

At the school level, Vedic mathematics lends itself for promoting commercial activities. There are online classes for children on Vedic mathematics, offline classes that combine Vedic mathematics with Abacus, books with title like *Vedic Math Made Easy*, *Vedic Math Workbook* for children and so on. Among the several other additional mathematics classes that urban middle-class children are forced to attend, apart from the mathematics they learn in school, Vedic mathematics is one. And the books and online classes build their own myths in addition to what is already present in the very idea of Vedic mathematics. Here are a few examples:

- Vedic math is also called Speed Maths. It is a very age-old system of mathematics. It was taught in ashrams in olden days & holds good for improving your math (aptitude) skills in modern day.
- This Vedic mathematics course aims to promote the traditional knowledge of Mathematics mastered by the mathematicians of ancient India.
- Vedic Maths is the World's fastest calculating system and was originated in ancient India. It enables performing calculations 10 times faster than the conventional method. It is an elaboration of the 16 sutras (and 13 sub-sutras) derived from Vedic calculating system as mentioned in the ancient Vedas (particularly 'The Atharva Veda') of India.

Interestingly, a few of the books also say that the tricks have nothing to do with Vedas though the book is called *Vedic Mathematics* or say that Vedic mathematics is another name for speed mathematics.

Vedic mathematics also receives regular of press coverage, partly because, ministers from the ruling BJP at the centre and from some state governments headed by BJP, make statements about introducing Vedic mathematics in school curriculum while speaking about the new Education Policy introduced in 2020. One such press report is about a call that a grade XII student, Usman Saifi, received from the Prime Minister Mr. Narendra Modi for topping the board examination; the prime minister congratulation Usman asks him to learn Vedic mathematics and teach his friends (TOI, 2020). There are websites dedicated to Vedic mathematics, YouTube videos, journals, seminars, conferences and offer for a career in Vedic mathematics. In all these references to Vedic mathematics, for some Vedic stands for ancient Vedas and for some others say it just stands for a set of computational tricks 10 times faster than standard methods.

Right wing political outfits such as Rashtriya Swayamsevak Sangh (RSS) have been making consistent demand that Vedic mathematics be incorporated in school curriculum. It is difficult to imagine if such a demand would be meaningful had the book been titled differently or if any other book offering 16 efficient formulas for fast computations would have achieved the cult status that Vedic mathematics has achieved.

A method behind the myth of Vedic mathematics

It would be naïve to think that the Shankaracharya came up with idea of naming the book ‘Vedic Mathematics’ to simply glorify the Vedic past. Both the content and the title of the book have significant role to play in fanning Hindu fanaticism. Manufacturing a glorious (mythical) past is part of the efforts by the fascists Hindutva forces to undermine what they would call ‘western’ knowledge across disciplines. They have also made false claims about Indian achievements in science and have attempted to rewrite the history of India with no regard for evidence. In fact, in the year 2014, Prime Minister Narendra Modi claimed that ancient India already had knowledge of plastic surgery and assisted reproductive technologies (Rahman, 2014). The strategy fascists use is the same: systematically create myths, false narratives, fictitious accounts, and base all claims about the superiority of Vedic knowledge on them, spread these among the common people, particularly among the Hindus, create a sense of having been wronged by the Islamic and colonial rulers and finally issue a call to set the history right. The power of the claims lies precisely in the fact that there is no way one can challenge them using reason or evidence- the discourse is not pitched at the level of academic engagement for one to counter them using logic and material evidence. In fact, the ‘western’ academic approach itself would be considered suspect.

In this scheme of things, it does not matter that what Vedic mathematics provides is a just a set of efficient algorithms that are consistent with what is being taught in schools now. The objective is not to replace the mathematics taught in school by ancient Indian mathematics; instead, it is to use the so-called Vedic mathematics to advance the Hindu

communal agenda. Imposing a set of formulae as Vedic mathematics, amounts to making a symbolic assertion about the superiority of Vedic knowledge.

The Shankaracharya achieves exactly this. In his own words,

Eversince (i.e., since several decades ago), we have been carrying on an incessant and strenuous campaign for the India-wide diffusion of all this scientific knowledge, by means of lectures, blackboard- demonstrations, regular classes and so on in schools, colleges, universities etc., all over the country and have been astounding our audiences everywhere with the wonders and marvels not to say, miracles of Indian Vedic mathematics. (Tirthaji, 1965, p. xv).

RSS affiliated Vidhya Bharati schools which cater to 3.4 million students from economically marginalized background from across the country teach five additional subjects apart from the subjects prescribed by central or state board of education to which the school is affiliated. Vedic mathematics is one of the five additional subjects. RSS and its associates make regular demand that school curriculum should be changed to align with Vedic knowledge. In 2002 when the BJP came to power at the centre, it changed the history curriculum and textbooks with no regard to academic rigour or to the constitutional values of secularism and harmony (Gohain, 2002; Tapar, 2002; Roy, 2002). Several states ruled by the BJP have revised their school curriculum and in the case of mathematics, they have introduced Vedic mathematics.

Though some of the prominent mathematicians have argued that there is nothing Vedic about Vedic mathematics and some of the books on Vedic mathematics brought out by private publishers also say the same, Hindutva outfits continue to propagate the myth about Vedic mathematics. Here is a sample from the book *Fundamentals and Applications of Vedic Mathematics* brought out by the Delhi State Council for Education Research and Training (Teotia, 2014):

Vedic mathematics forms part of Jyotish Shastra which is one of the six parts of Vedangas. The Jyotish Shastra or Astronomy is made up of three parts called Skandas. A Skanda means the big branch of a tree shooting out of the trunk. (p. 3)

The “Vedic mathematics” is called so because of its origin from Vedas. To be more specific, it has originated from “Atharva Vedas” the fourth Veda. “Atharva Veda” deals with the branches like Engineering, Mathematics, sculpture, Medicine, and all other sciences with which we are today aware of. (p. 7)

Vedic scholars did not use figures for big numbers in their numerical notation. Instead, they preferred to use the Sanskrit alphabets, with each alphabet constituting a number. Several mantras, in fact, denote numbers; that includes the famed Gayatri Mantra, which adds to 108 when decoded. (p. 8)

This book not only adds its own twist to the Vedic connection, but it also makes a direct link between mathematics and religion by referring to mantras. It must be noted that the famous Gayathri mantra can be chanted by only males and even among them only brahmins can chant the whole of it.

Vedic mathematics and symbolic violence

The need for imposing Vedic knowledge arises only if there are those who might not be inclined to take interest in it. Ancient Indian mathematics had significant contributions from Buddhist and Jain traditions. Islamic art, architecture, music, literature, mathematics, and science have contributed richly to the cultures in India. Historically, apart from the dominant classical tradition in mathematics, there were also vernacular traditions in mathematics brought into existence by those who were engaged in productive labour. The name 'Vedic mathematics', will not invoke images of any of these. Caste is fundamental to Hinduism – there is no way that one can be a Hindu without belonging to one caste or the other. Caste system is a hierarchical system with brahmins at the top of the hierarchy. Access to Vedas was not equally available to all Hindus. Vedas were written/chanted in Sanskrit, a language accessible only to brahmin men and perhaps the kings while others used Prakrit. Dalits, who were/are treated as untouchables had no right to even hear the chanting of Vedas. Similarly, those who belong to Islam or Christianity had no access to Vedas. The same goes for several tribal groups who do not even identify as Hindus. The so called 'Vedic mathematics' therefore stands for a form of mathematics accessible only to those who had the right to read Sanskrit, namely the brahmin men and few other powerful elite men. The act of imposing a set of 16 formulas as 'Vedic mathematics' on everyone would therefore be hegemonic.

It is in the name of Vedic religion that people were divided hierarchically into castes. It is in the name of Vedas that Dalits were treated as untouchables, subjected to humiliation, structural violence, poverty and denied their basic human rights. What pride can they take in Vedic mathematics? What fascination would Vedic mathematics hold for students from non-brahmin castes while mathematical knowledge embedded in their traditional caste-based work has no place in it? Why would Muslims and Christians in India – many of whom converted in the hope of escaping the caste-based violence and humiliation- want to take pride in Vedic mathematics when they face systematic attack from the Hindu right wing? Wouldn't inclusion of Vedic mathematics in school curriculum alienate these students and is that not a form of symbolic violence?

Conclusion

Mathematics education in India is desperately in need of systematic research to understand the factors that are responsible for the underrepresentation of Dalits, tribals, religious minorities, and women in mathematics; for the socio-economically marginalized, mathematics functions as a gatekeeper, ensuring that they continue to provide cheap labour and this needs to be studied and addressed. Similarly, there is an urgent need to document alternate forms of mathematical knowledge embedded in various forms of traditional work and local culture as part of people's knowledge of mathematics. Rather than urging the government to take these up seriously, the Hindutva forces call for the introduction of Vedic mathematics in school curriculum with a clear intension of spreading Hindu religious fundamentalism. Even as they belittle western knowledge, they use whatever recognition

Vedic mathematics receives form the west to their advantage. Given this, the international academic community committed to social justice has the dual responsibility of being inclusive of the geopolitically underrepresented on the one hand, and sensitive to the local hierarchies on the other, in order to stay true its commitment.

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